

External Report for Logic-Rx

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A Pseudocode of *Logic-Rx*

Algorithm 1 gives a high-level sketch of one *Logic-Rx* inference step, instantiating the main framework and its three-tier diagnostic cascade. The names follow the paper: π_θ , Φ , and Σ are the translator, lifter, and solver in the formalize–lift–solve pipeline; each tier $\mathcal{T}_k = (\text{Det}_k, \text{Loc}_k, \text{Fix}_k)$ for $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ is the abstract detector–localizer–repair triple; *Fusion* and the *IR Report* are the consolidation step and shared repair record used by the framework. The pseudocode treats every tier component as a black box and shows only the framework-level control flow.

Algorithm 1 *Logic-Rx* inference for one sample x .

Require: translator π_θ ; lifter Φ ; solver Σ ; tiers $\mathcal{T}_k = (\text{Det}_k, \text{Loc}_k, \text{Fix}_k)$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Ensure: prediction \hat{y} .

Convention. Each call $\mathcal{T}_k(\cdot, \text{IR Report})$ runs Det_k on its argument and applies Fix_k to every finding; the deterministic branch rewrites the argument via Φ , the residual branch attaches a hint at $\text{Loc}_k(\cdot)$ to *IR Report* via FUSION.

```
1: IR Report  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $t \leftarrow \pi_\theta(x)$  ▷ generate textual formalization
3:  $(t, \text{IR Report}) \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_1(t, \text{IR Report})$  ▷ at parse: surface check on  $t$ 
4: if  $\Phi$  can lift  $t$  then
5:    $\mathcal{I} \leftarrow \Phi(t)$  ▷ lift into the typed IR
6:    $(\mathcal{I}, \text{IR Report}) \leftarrow \mathcal{T}_2(\mathcal{I}, x, \text{IR Report})$  ▷ post-lift: static check on  $\mathcal{I}$  (and  $x$ )
7:    $r \leftarrow \Sigma(\mathcal{I})$  ▷ execute
8:   IR Report  $\leftarrow \mathcal{T}_3(r, \mathcal{I}, \text{IR Report})$  ▷ post-execute: runtime check on  $r$ 
9:   if IR Report =  $\emptyset$  then
10:    return  $r$  ▷ no detector fires;  $r$  is the traceable answer
11:   end if
12: end if ▷ else:  $\mathcal{T}_2, \mathcal{T}_3$  skipped — no  $\mathcal{I}$  to analyse
13:  $t \leftarrow \pi_\theta(x, \text{IR Report})$  ▷ one bundled LLM-repair call
14: return  $\Sigma(\Phi(t))$ 
```

B Dataset Statistics

The table below reports the per-dataset gold-label distributions of the dev splits used in the experiments, with n matching the evaluation setup. The three FOL datasets are near-balanced across their respective label spaces; ProverQA is slightly skewed toward `Undetermined` on every depth bin. LogicalDeduction is multiple-choice with 3–7 options per instance (60, 100, and 140 instances at the three option counts respectively); answer letters therefore skew toward `A–C` simply because every puzzle exposes those letters whereas only the 7-option puzzles expose `F` and `G`.

Table 1: Gold-label distribution per dataset. ProofWriter uses `{T, F, U}` for `{True, False, Unknown}`; ProverQA uses `{T, F, U}` for `{True, False, Undetermined}`; PrOntoQA is binary. LogicalDeduction is multiple-choice; we report counts per answer letter `A...G`.

Dataset	Split	n	Label distribution
ProofWriter	depth-5 dev	600	T:200 / F:200 / U:200
PrOntoQA	closed-vocab dev	500	T:258 / F:242
LogicalDeduction	BBH	300	A:64, B:60, C:62, D:31, E:45, F:21, G:17
ProverQA Easy	synthetic, depth 1–2	300	T:87 / F:81 / U:132
ProverQA Medium	synthetic, depth 3–5	300	T:91 / F:89 / U:120
ProverQA Hard	synthetic, depth 6–9	300	T:108 / F:78 / U:114

C Prompt Example: FOL Formalizer

```
# Skill: fol-formalizer

Translate the user's NL question into plain first-order logic.
Emit one formula per line, each ending with `.`. End the block with a
single `? <goal>.` query line. Each top-level line ends with
`// <verbatim NL sentence>` for provenance.

## Allowed vocabulary

- Connectives: `forall`, `exists`, `->`, `<->`, `and`, `or`, `not`,
  `=`, `!=`.
- Lowercase predicates, constants, and bound variables.

## Polarity convention for queries

For a surface-negated NL question (e.g. "X is not Y"), keep the query
atom POSITIVE and add `? polarity = negated.` on its own line.

## Examples

NL: "All cats are animals."
forall x (cat(x) -> animal(x)). // All cats are animals.

NL: "Dave is not furry."
not furry(dave). // Dave is not furry.

NL: "Is Yuri tall?"
? tall(yuri). // Is Yuri tall?
```

```
NL: "The mouse does not need the rabbit?"
? needs(mouse, rabbit). // The mouse does not need the rabbit.
? polarity = negated.

## Rules

- Relational verbs use prefix form: `sees(cat, mouse)` -- never
  `sees_mouse(cat)` nor NL-infix `cat sees mouse`.
- The predicate head is the bare verb or adjective stem only -- do not
  prefix it with an argument's noun phrase. Write
  `eats(bald_eagle, bear).` not `bald_eagle_eats(bald_eagle, bear).`;
  write `cold(lion).` not `lion_cold(lion).`.
- Emit exactly one line per NL sentence in CONTEXT -- including
  negated sentences. "X is not Y." -> `not Y(X). // X is not Y.` Do
  not skip a sentence because it is negated. Never both `P(x).` and
  `not P(x).` for the same sentence.
- Predicate arguments are variables or constants only -- never other
  atoms. Write `nice(x)` and `cold(x)`, not `nice(cold(x))`.
- Negation is the `not` operator -- never fused into a predicate name.
  Write `not big(lion)`, never `not_big(lion)`.
- A name is either a constant or a predicate, never both. If a name
  appears as an argument (e.g. `bob` in `nice(bob)`), do not use it
  as a predicate head.
- No declaration lines (`sort`, `pred`, `func`, `const`).
- End with exactly one `? <query>.` line.
```

The per-line // <verbatim NL sentence> trailer is the back-pointer that lets \mathcal{T}_2 check NL-alignment between \mathcal{I} and x : an IR line whose comment matches no NL sentence is flagged as fabricated, and an NL sentence with no matching comment is flagged as uncovered.

D IR and IR Report Schemas

The typed intermediate representation used by the framework is realised by two mode-specific Pydantic models, both wrapped at run time by a single *IR Report* that carries the shared addressing substrate used by FUSION. The sketches below match the implementation; auxiliary serialisation and backward-compatibility fields have been elided.

D.1 Verdict-mode IR — FOLLogicIR

```
class FOLLogicIR(BaseModel):
    sorts: List[SortDef] # uninterpreted or enum sorts
    predicates: List[PredicateDef] # boolean-valued relations
    functions: List[FunctionDef] # value-returning, e.g. f: Person -> Season
    premises: List[FOLFormula] # closed asserted formulas
    query: FOLFormula # closed goal formula
    query_polarity: "affirmative" | "negated"

class FOLFormula(BaseModel): # recursive node
    kind: "atom" | "neg" | "and" | "or" | "implies" | "iff"
    | "forall" | "exists" | "equality"
    predicate, args # populated for kind == "atom"
    operands # for the logical connectives
    variables, body # for the two quantifiers
    left, right # for kind == "equality"
    source_span: str # verbatim NL sentence (NL back-pointer)
    provenance: Optional[Provenance] # parser line/column for repair targeting
```

D.2 Letter-mode IR — ConstraintIR

```

class ConstraintIR(BaseModel):
    variables: List[VarDecl]          # each (name, sort in {Int, Real, Bool})
    constraints: List[Constraint]     # each: an Expression that evaluates to Bool
    question_type: "satisfiability" | "validity"
    | "optimization" | "all_solutions"
    objective, objective_direction   # for question_type == "optimization"

class Constraint(BaseModel):
    expr: Expression                 # tree of arith/compare/logical/var/const nodes
    label: str                       # human-readable description; carries the
    # verbatim NL trailer from the 4-section DSL

# Expression nodes (discriminated union):
# VarRef(name)                       # variable reference
# ConstVal(value)                   # int / float / bool / str literal
# ArithOp(op in {+,-,*,/,mod}, args[2])
# CompareOp(op in {=,!=,<,>,<=,>=}, args[2])
# LogicalOp(op in {and,or,not,implies,iff}, args)

```

D.3 Unified IRReport

```

class IRReport(BaseModel):
    # ---- source
    raw_fol: str                    # the LLM's textual formalization t
    nl_context, nl_question: str

    # ---- IR content (flattened FOLLogicIR fields for the verdict path)
    sorts, predicates, functions: List[...]
    premises: List[FOLFormula]
    query: Optional[FOLFormula]
    query_polarity: "affirmative" | "negated"
    parse_ok: bool                 # True iff Phi succeeded on t

    # ---- diagnostics (filled by the three-tier cascade)
    diagnostics: List[Diagnostic]   # the IR Report substrate

    # ---- execution trace
    solver_path: "prolog" | "z3_fol" | "none"
    rendered_program: Optional[str] # what Sigma was given, for audit
    solver_result: Optional[SolverResult]
    raw_conclusion: "entailed" | "refuted" | "not_entailed"
    | "unknown" | "execution_failed" | None

    # ---- final
    predicted_label: "True" | "False" | "Unknown"
    world_assumption: "owa" | "cwa"

    # ---- meta
    llm_calls: int                 # 1 (no repair) or 2--3 (with repair)
    repair_fired: bool
    repair_rolled_back: bool

```

IRReport is the concrete realisation of the framework’s shared addressing substrate: every detection-level finding becomes a **Diagnostic** attached to this single object, which FUSION then organises into the IR Report consumed by the deterministic and LLM repair channels. A parallel field-set is used for letter-mode samples (replacing the FOL fields with their **ConstraintIR** analogues); the diagnostic and trace layers are shared.

D.4 Detection-level finding — Diagnostic

```

class Diagnostic(BaseModel):

```

```

type:          DiagnosticType          # e.g. fol_parse_error, non_horn,
                                         # signature_arity_conflict, z3_unsat_core
error_kind:   ErrorKind                # finer-grained label (e.g. neg_in_head)
severity:     "info" | "warn" | "repair_trigger"
raw_message:  str                      # original source message

# ---- localisation (Loc_k)
failing_predicate, failing_goal: Optional[str]
source_nl:    Optional[str]           # NL sentence the issue traces back to
line, col:    Optional[int]           # 1-based position in raw_fol
lines:        List[int]               # multi-line cases (signature checks)
expected_tokens: List[str]           # parser's "expected one of ..."
snippet:      Optional[str]           # offending fragment of raw_fol

details:      Dict[str, Any]          # type-specific extras

```

A `Diagnostic` with `severity = "repair_trigger"` is what advances the LLM-repair channel of Algorithm 1; `"info"` and `"warn"` records remain in the IR Report for audit but do not by themselves fire π_θ .

E Open-Source Model Evaluation

Table 2 reports additional results collected with Qwen3-8B and Gemma3-12B through an Ollama backend. The pattern is consistent with the main experiments: *Logic-Rx* is the strongest formalization method on most datasets and is especially robust on LogicalDeduction, where single-channel repair and sampling-based baselines are less stable.

Table 2: Open-source model evaluation via an Ollama backend. Entries are accuracy percentages, reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Best value per model and dataset is shown in bold.

Model	Method	ProofWriter	PrOntoQA	LogicalDeduction
Qwen3-8B	CoT	85.90 \pm 0.30	100.00 \pm 0.00	88.20 \pm 1.10
	Logic-LM	87.80 \pm 0.40	97.00 \pm 0.50	96.70 \pm 0.30
	LINC	95.00 \pm 0.00	97.40 \pm 0.00	87.30 \pm 0.00
	Logic-Rx	97.80 \pm 0.20	98.10 \pm 0.40	97.70 \pm 0.30
Gemma3-12B	CoT	95.30 \pm 1.40	97.90 \pm 0.10	94.00 \pm 0.60
	Logic-LM	88.80 \pm 1.20	94.00 \pm 0.50	78.30 \pm 1.20
	LINC	94.70 \pm 0.00	95.60 \pm 0.00	84.40 \pm 1.30
	Logic-Rx	97.50 \pm 0.40	98.20 \pm 0.20	98.10 \pm 0.20

F Worked Examples: Diagnostic Tiers and Bundled Repair

This section provides three examples illustrating how *Logic-Rx* constructs an IR-centered repair report from different diagnostic sources. All examples use

entailment-style inputs, but they expose different failure modes. Example 1 illustrates bundled static repair at \mathcal{T}_2 . Example 2 illustrates surface-level repair at \mathcal{T}_1 . Example 3 illustrates a runtime-level defect detected at \mathcal{T}_3 . Together, the examples show how heterogeneous diagnostics are localized to shared IR objects and converted into targeted repair guidance.

F.1 Example 1: Bundled Static Repair at \mathcal{T}_2

The first example shows a formalization that is accepted by the surface grammar but contains two coupled structural defects in the typed IR.

Input. The natural-language instance is:

Context: “Bob is a dog. Every dog is a mammal. All mammals are warm-blooded.”
Question: “Is Bob warm-blooded?”
Gold label: TRUE.

First formalization. The initial LLM output is syntactically acceptable, but line 2 is semantically broken: it uses `dog` with arity 2 and omits the implication required by a universal rule.

```
dog(bob).
forall X (dog(X, mammal)).
forall X (mammal(X) -> warm_blooded(X)).
warm_blooded(bob)?
```

Diagnostics. The surface grammar accepts the text, so no \mathcal{T}_1 signal is emitted. The typed IR, however, exposes two \mathcal{T}_2 defects at the same location:

- `signature_arity_conflict`: `dog` appears as both `dog/1` and `dog/2`;
- `forall_no_arrow`: the universal premise has a bare atom body rather than an implication.

If these defects were not repaired, the solver would fail to derive the query, and the open-world mapper would return UNKNOWN.

Bundled repair. The repair builder emits one prompt containing both localized hints: use a consistent arity for `dog`, and rewrite the universal premise as an implication. The revised formalization is:

```
dog(bob).
forall X (dog(X) -> mammal(X)).
forall X (mammal(X) -> warm_blooded(X)).
warm_blooded(bob)?
```

Re-lifting the repaired formalization removes both diagnostics. The solver then derives the expected `dog`–`mammal`–`warm-blooded` chain for Bob, yielding the correct label TRUE.

Table 3: Pipeline trace for Example 1. The same lifter Φ and solver Σ are reused before and after repair; only the LLM is called again.

Stage	Operation	State
1	$\pi_\theta(x) \rightarrow t$	Plain-text FOL is produced; line 2 contains two coupled defects.
2	$\Phi(t) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}$	The text lifts, but the IR records both <code>dog/1</code> and <code>dog/2</code> .
3	$\text{Det}_2(\mathcal{I})$	<code>signature_arity_conflict</code> and <code>forall_no_arrow</code> fire.
4	P_{rep}	Both diagnostics are bundled into one structured repair request.
5	$\pi_\theta(x, t) \rightarrow t'$	The LLM fixes the predicate arity and missing implication in one pass.
6	$\Phi(t'), \Sigma$	The corrected program is lifted, solved by Prolog, and mapped to <code>TRUE</code> .

Table 4: Selected IRReport fields before and after bundled repair in Example 1.

Field	Before repair	After repair
<i>predicates</i>	<code>dog/1, dog/2, mammal/1, and warm_blooded/1</code>	<code>dog/1, mammal/1, and warm_blooded/1</code>
<i>premises</i>	line 2 is a universal over a bare atom	line 2 is a universal implication
<i>signature</i>	<code>dog ↦ {1, 2}</code>	<code>dog ↦ {1}</code>
<i>diagnostics</i>	arity conflict; missing implication	none
<i>solver result</i>	<code>not_entailed</code> ; predicted <code>UNKNOWN</code>	<code>entailed</code> ; predicted <code>TRUE</code>
<i>LLM calls</i>	1	2

Takeaway. This example illustrates bundled repair at the static tier. The surface form is accepted, but the typed IR makes both defects addressable through the same premise and predicate-signature fields. *Logic-Rx* therefore repairs the two coupled defects in one revision step rather than through sequential single-error patching.

F.2 Example 2: Surface Repair at \mathcal{T}_1

The second example illustrates a surface-level defect that prevents the lifter from constructing a valid typed IR.

Input.

Context: “Alice is a student. Every student is diligent.”

Question: “Is Alice diligent?”

Gold label: `TRUE`.

First formalization. The first-pass output contains a malformed universal rule. The closing parenthesis is missing in line 2:

```
student(alice).
forall X (student(X) -> diligent(X).
diligent(alice)?
```

Diagnostics. Unlike Example 1, this formalization cannot be lifted because the parser rejects the text. The failure is therefore detected at \mathcal{T}_1 :

- **grammar_rejection**: line 2 has an unmatched parenthesis;
 - **span_localization**: the rejected span is localized to the universal rule.
- Since no valid \mathcal{I} is constructed, \mathcal{T}_2 and \mathcal{T}_3 cannot inspect the formalization.

Repair. The repair report contains a surface-localized correction:

Line 2 is rejected by the parser because the universal rule has an unmatched parenthesis. Close the formula after `diligent(X)` and keep the rest of the formalization unchanged.

The repaired formalization is:

```
student(alice).
forall X (student(X) -> diligent(X)).
diligent(alice)?
```

After repair, Φ constructs a valid typed IR, and the solver derives `diligent(alice)` from `student(alice)` and the universal rule.

Table 5: Pipeline trace for Example 2. The defect is detected before typed IR construction, so repair is driven by the surface diagnostic.

Stage	Operation	State
1	$\pi_\theta(x) \rightarrow t$	Plain-text FOL is produced with an unmatched parenthesis in line 2.
2	$\text{Det}_1(t)$	The grammar rejects the universal rule and returns a localized parser message.
3	$\Phi(t)$	Lifting is blocked because no valid typed IR can be constructed.
4	P_{rep}	The repair request names the rejected span and the parser-level cause.
5	$\pi_\theta(x, t) \rightarrow t'$	The LLM repairs the malformed rule.
6	$\Phi(t'), \Sigma$	The corrected program is lifted, solved, and mapped to <code>TRUE</code> .

Takeaway. This example illustrates why \mathcal{T}_1 is necessary. When the surface form is malformed, no typed IR exists for later tiers. Repair must therefore be driven by parser-localized feedback before static or runtime diagnostics can be applied.

F.3 Example 3: Runtime Repair at \mathcal{T}_3

The third example illustrates a formalization that is parseable and liftable, but fails at solver execution because the query uses a predicate name that is not grounded by the program.

Input.

Context: “Nina is a bird. Every bird can fly.”

Question: “Can Nina fly?”

Gold label: TRUE.

First formalization. The first-pass output is syntactically valid:

```
bird(nina).
forall X (bird(X) -> can_fly(X)).
fly(nina)?
```

The program can be parsed and lifted into the typed IR. However, the rule defines `can_fly/1`, while the query asks for `fly/1`. If the solver treats undefined or ungrounded query predicates as execution-level failures, this mismatch is exposed at runtime.

Diagnostics. The tiers fire as follows:

- \mathcal{T}_1 does not fire because the formalization is parseable.
- \mathcal{T}_2 constructs a valid IR and records the predicates `bird/1`, `can_fly/1`, and `fly/1`.
- \mathcal{T}_3 fires a runtime/result diagnostic because the query predicate `fly/1` is not supported by any premise or rule head. The diagnostic is mapped back to the query object.

The IR-centered repair report is:

IR Report

```
- Tier: T3 / runtime-result
  Target: query
  Defect: query predicate fly/1 is unsupported by the program
  Repair hint: align the query predicate with the rule head can_fly/1
```

Repair. The repair request is:

The rule derives `can_fly(X)` from `bird(X)`, but the query asks for `fly(nina)`. Align the query predicate with the rule head by changing the query to `can_fly(nina)`. Keep the premises unchanged.

The repaired formalization is:

```
bird(nina).
forall X (bird(X) -> can_fly(X)).
can_fly(nina)?
```

The solver now derives `can_fly(nina)` from `bird(nina)`, and the final answer is mapped to `TRUE`.

Table 6: Pipeline trace for Example 3. The formalization is parseable and liftable, but the solver exposes an unsupported query predicate.

Stage	Operation	State
1	$\pi_\theta(x) \rightarrow t$	Plain-text FOL is produced and is syntactically valid.
2	$\Phi(t) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}$	The lifted IR contains both <code>can_fly/1</code> and <code>fly/1</code> .
3	$\Sigma(\mathcal{I})$	The solver cannot support the query predicate <code>fly/1</code> .
4	$\text{Det}_3(r)$	The runtime/result diagnostic is localized to the query object.
5	P_{rep}	The repair request asks the LLM to align the query with the rule head.
6	$\Phi(t'), \Sigma$	The corrected program is lifted, solved, and mapped to <code>TRUE</code> .

Takeaway. This example illustrates the role of \mathcal{T}_3 . The formalization is well-formed enough to pass surface and lifting stages, but the solver result exposes a defect that only becomes visible during execution. Mapping the runtime finding back to the query object allows *Logic-Rx* to produce a targeted repair rather than a generic solver-error retry.

F.4 Summary

The three examples cover complementary failure modes. Example 1 shows a static bundled repair where two coupled defects are exposed by the typed IR. Example 2 shows a surface-level error that blocks IR construction and must be repaired before later tiers can run. Example 3 shows a runtime-level defect that is only visible after solver execution. Across all three cases, the key mechanism is the same: *Logic-Rx* localizes heterogeneous diagnostics to shared formal objects and assembles them into structured repair guidance.